
DELIVERABLE 2.1

Water Sports Tourism Education Stakeholders Map

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Glossary

Abbreviation / Acronym	Meaning
AUTH/SJMC	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki/ School of Journalism and mass media
EASME	European Agency for SMEs
EC	European Commission
EMFF	European Maritime and Fisheries Fund
ENAT	European Network for Accessible Tourism
ETIS	European Tourism Indicators System
GA	Grant Agreement
GEJI	Global Environmental Journalism Initiative
IKO	International Kitesurf Organisation
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Officer (EC)
PSB	Project Steering Board
QA	Quality Assurance
SUP	Stand Up Paddle
UAG	User Advisory Group
UC	Usage Cases
WPL	Work Package Leaders
CEDEFOP	European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training
DoA	Description of Action
ECREA	European Communication Research and Education Association
EFJ	European Federation of Journalists
EJTA	European Journalism Training Association
EOT	Hellenic Tourism Organization
ESN	Erasmus Student Network
ETIS	European Tourism Indicators System
EUPREra	European Public Relations Education and Research Association
GR	Greece
IAMCR	International Association for Media and Communication Research

IKO	International Kitesurf Organization
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IPRA	International Public Relations Association
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
ILO	International Labour Organisation
LLC	Lifelong Learning Centres
MOOC	Massive Online Courses
TR	Turkey
UNWTO	United Nations World Tourism Organization
WP	Work Package
WTTC	World Travel and Tourism Council

1 Summary

The current document is the Water Sports Tourism Education Stakeholders Map for the EU funded project entitled '[NAUTILUS – Education and Certification Framework for Blue Career in Water Sports Tourism](#)'.

The purpose of the current document is to draw attention to the general framework of the water sports tourism trends, educational needs and challenges, and to present the design, development and implementation of a mapping process in the Water Sports Tourism environment and categorisation of the key stakeholders in the industry and the Education and Training sector.

The Water Sports Tourism Stakeholders map will be used as a guide to establish the needed collaboration mechanisms for reliable and effective cooperation among all involved actors in the water sports tourism sector.

Furthermore, the findings of the study for the education and training offer for water sports tourism reveal three main education models provided by a) universities, b) colleges and academies for physical education and sports, and c) water sports associations and organisations that offer entirely different knowledge base and skills and there is not specific specialisation for water sports professionals.

The mapping results and the dynamic and continuously updated database that accompanies them will guide us to design a skills needs and training needs analysis. This analysis will identify the professional profile of the water sports tourism workforce and will lead to the development of the NAUTILUS-Education and Certification Framework.

[This document is submitted to EASME according to the DoA by the end of M8 \(June 2020\).](#)

2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose

The Water Sports Tourism Education Stakeholders Map for the EU funded project entitled '[NAUTILUS – Education and Certification Framework for Blue Career in Water Sports Tourism](#)' is the first attempt to map the Water Sports Tourism environment and their educational and training sector to identify the key stakeholders, in order to establish the needed collaboration mechanisms for reliable and effective cooperation.

This map consists of two major categories:

- a) the Water Sports Tourism Stakeholders
- b) The Education and Training providers for Water Sports & Tourism

The first group of stakeholders consists of several categories that were identified and catalogued.

The second categorisation includes all types of education and training offered by formal education institutions, and training programs offered by informal and non-formal VET providers for blue careers, focusing on hospitality, sports tourism, coastal/ maritime tourism and water sports training.

This mapping procedure identifies the water sports tourism education and training models that will be evaluated in the next step of this project after the skills and training needs analysis of the water sports tourism professionals.

The structure of this document:

Chapter 1 is the summary, and **Chapter 2** presents the introduction and the general framework of the current study, identifying the links between water sports and tourism, and the current challenges and issues in the coastal tourism industry. Chapter 2 introduces the topic of education and training in the water sports tourism sector and describes the methodology used for this study.

Chapter 3 presents the findings of this study regarding the two broad categories of this map

Final Chapters cover the conclusions, and limitations of the study. In the Appendix section can be found the mapping tool for the Education and Training providers for Water Sports & Tourism.

2.2 Scope of use

We will use this map to understand the existing education and training environment better and assess its alignment with the industry. This map is based on a database with contact details and complete analysis of the educational and training models and programmes. This will be used as a guide to establish the needed collaboration mechanisms for reliable and effective cooperation among all involved actors of our value chain.

This map is to be used by all partners and stakeholders involved in the NAUTILUS project but can also be used by all interested parties who would like to focus and study this sector in depth. Water sports tourism includes various forms and is a subcategory of the coastal and recreational tourism, which is also categorised under the broader category of the nautical tourism (Galatsopoulou & Kenterelidou,

2020). Due to this broad sector and its classifications, many issues, topics, trends and demands remain understudied and could be thoroughly examined.

The scope of this map remains dynamic as it is based on a databank which is constantly updated and enriched.

3 Background

3.1.1 Water Sports & Tourism

Water sports have a long tradition and include many different forms. They are practiced on or in/under the water (surface or underwater sports), may use the wind, the water stream, the waves, paddles or a motor, for power. They can be practiced on a board or vessel, may use different equipment and can be experienced in different water areas (sea, river, lake, ocean). Some categories of water sports are listed as 'extreme' sports due to the danger they include, the speed, the height, the tricks participants must perform, and the physiological exertion that is required (Cox, 2009). Extreme sports are also known as adventure sports and are labelled 'alternative', 'X', 'gravity', 'lifestyle' and 'action sports' (Breivik, 2010). According to Breivik (2010) they contain elements of challenge, excitement and risk, and they require skills related not only to the body but the mind. The reward is a strong blend of wonderful sensations and experiences. This reward in addition to the sense of freedom and the release of fear (Brymer & Schweitzer, 2013), as well as the development of 'a deep relationship with the natural world' (Brymer & Gray, 2009) are some of the motivations for participating in extreme sports that have become **a lifestyle and a tourism trend**.

Water sports tourism is a subcategory of the coastal and maritime tourism and contributes to the blue economy and job creation in coastal regions. It is also part of the Blue Growth strategy launched by the European Union to ensure the sustainable development of the European Seas and Coasts (European Commission, 2012).

The value chain in the coastal and water-based tourism is recognised by national tourism organisations, and during the last three decades key stakeholders have been focusing on water sports tourism demand and offer and have been examining destinations' strengths and weaknesses for potential development of water-related tourism (Biedenkapp & Stührmann, 2004; Fadda, 2019).

According to the Blue Economy report 2020 about coastal tourism ¹:

The EU welcomed 500 million international tourists (overnight visitors) in 2017, accounting for 40 % of the world's total. International tourism receipts reached €342 billion, representing 31 % of world-wide tourism earnings².

*In 2018, just over half (51.7 %) of the EU's tourist accommodation establishments were located in **coastal areas**. Visitors to coastal areas were generally higher in southern EU Member States, which are generally more conducive to beach holidays due to climatic*

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/sites/maritimeaffairs/files/2020_06_blueeconomy-2020-ld_final.pdf

² European Commission. 2018. European Union Tourism Trends (<https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/vto/content/2018-eu-tourism-trends-report>).

conditions. In 2018, coastal areas accounted for more than three quarters of the total nights spent in tourist accommodation across Malta, Cyprus, Greece, Croatia, Portugal and Spain. As part of EU's Blue Growth strategy, the coastal and maritime tourism sector has been identified as an area with special potential to foster a smart, sustainable and inclusive Europe. Sustained growth in tourism has been instrumental in supporting the economic recovery of many EU Member States, largely contributing to job creation, GDP and the balance of payments.

3.1.2 Challenges and Issues

The Blue Economy report 2020 (EC, 2020) refers to the coastal communities that are mainly composed of SMEs and micro-enterprises which are vulnerable to economic, financial and political changes. In addition, coastal areas are prone to a number of climate change related impacts that affect directly tourism facilities and activities.

Seasonality in coastal tourism is another issue to be considered. European seas and coasts host many water sports schools, clubs, centres, and resorts, providing services for water sports tourism and leisure during a period of 3-6 months per year. Due to seasonality of the job and lack of career opportunities this sector, as the most sectors in coastal tourism, is not attracting or maintain enough skilled personnel which leads to problems in service quality and competitiveness (EC, 2013).

Water sports tourism, as subcategory and fast-growing sector of the coastal and maritime tourism demands multi-skilled and educated professionals.

A new challenge that we are facing is to foster local employability for blue growth and sustainability in the coastal and rural areas.

3.1.3 Education and Training in Water Sports Tourism

Micro-business employers interviewed in several studies identify skills gaps and persistent recruitment difficulties which leads to downsizing, deskilling and overseas recruitment (Haven-Tang & Jones, 2008). Several studies on tourism education and training identify similar difficulties and new challenges in tourism education and examine programmes that prepare students to meet the labour needs of the tourism industry (Sheldon et al., 2007; Fidgeon, 2010; Castiglioni et al., 2017). The nexus between skills, training, and competitiveness is the focal point of studies examining hospitality education (Barron, 2008; Griffin, 2020), vocational training and curriculum development (Baum, 2002 ; Elliot & Joppe, 2009), hospitality industry needs (Lolli, 2013) and competencies (Marneros et al., 2020).

Based on the results of the MELTEMI PROJECT (EASME/EMFF/2016/1.2.1.12/03/SI2.765242 – MELTEMI) about the training needs of the blue careers, the difficulties that were encountered can be summarised here:

1. **Seasonal and mobile workers with different knowledge background.** Graduate students with hospitality degrees with different skills from those that are needed, or experienced water sports instructors with no theoretical knowledge about hospitality and guest services.
2. **Watersports instructors without knowledge** about the local area, its culture, environment and people.

3. **Not enough time and no structured plan** to train or educate the diverse workforce types.
4. **Safety was often overlooked**, especially by more experienced professionals
5. **Watersports instructors are often intimidated or reluctant to work with people with disabilities** because they fear they lack the tools to accommodate them.

Results of the training needs analysis that was conducted in 2018 in the framework of the MELTEMI Project for the development of a training syllabus for the NAUTICAL ROUTES professionals among others demonstrated the need for:

- a) **Knowledge of hospitality** services, management and tourism marketing
- b) **Soft skills:** language and communication skills, risk management, team working, resilience, leadership, cultural awareness.
- c) **Safety skills:** life guarding, first aid, emergency response, drawing prevention, self-survival and emergency action, rescue.
- d) **Inclusiveness training:** equip Water Sports Tourism Professionals with the knowledge, tools and attitude to provide an excellent, safe and rewarding service to people with disabilities.

Moreover, the analysis of **Customers Satisfaction Reports/ Reviews** and their Comments on Social Media about the SME's personnel and the customer services confirmed our assumption that blue professionals with: ***ocean literacy & increased knowledge about the specific travel destination*** can add value to the touristic product in coastal areas. Blue Professionals can act as local ambassadors for the promotion of the specific travel destination and can raise awareness about the preservation of our seas and the aquaculture.

Water sports tourism is a fast growing and important sector in the blue economy, but due to its broad categories and different forms there is not a specific **profile of the Water Sports Tourism professionals**. This profile would identify the specific skills and learning needs that will lead to the best educational and training pathway.

The current education and training paths and programmes offered for water sports tourism is the primary focus of this study in order to identify if they satisfy the real needs of the water sports tourism industry.

4 Methodology

4.1 Research Questions

1. What is the educational and training offer in water sports tourism in Europe?
2. Who are the water sports tourism education and training providers?
3. Who are the water sports tourism stakeholders?
4. What kind of certification/ accreditation there is?
5. Who can be trained and what are the requirements for someone to be accepted for training?
6. What are the types of educational/ training programmes?
7. What is the mode of delivery?
8. What are the learning objectives and the expected learning outcomes?

4.2 Method

Two research groups were formed and each of them consisted of senior and junior researchers. The first group consisted of experienced water sports instructors and managers of the Surf Club Keros who are familiar with the water sports industry and the technical terms and knowledge. This group was responsible for the mapping of the water sports tourism stakeholders. For this extensive mapping procedure, a data base was established with all stakeholders' categories and their contact details. This database and specifically the 'media' category were enriched by the junior researchers of the School of Journalism and Mass Communications of the Aristotle University.

The other research group from the Aristotle University worked on the mapping of the educational and training offer in water sports tourism in Europe. Two pilot phases concluded to the construction of a mapping tool, developed in a google form to collect all data.

The collection of data was through online web-search. The aim was to search for the educational and training offer in water sports tourism in formal, informal and non-formal educational settings and programmes. A list of terms was used for the search and mapping such as: "tourism" AND "education", "vocational training", "water sports tourism education", "water sports tourism training", "water sports trainer", "water sports academy", "water sports AND tourism", "Curriculum", "Course" "AND water sports tourism", "higher education AND water sports tourism", "water sports tourism AND adult education/ training", etc.

Mapping Tool

The pilot mapping phase indicated the following variables and questions for the mapping procedure:

1. Training/educational providers:
 - Higher Education/University/Faculty/School/Department (formal education)
 - Public/Private Academy or College (formal education)
 - Public/Private Vocational Education and Training (VET) school
 - VET (Vocational Education and Training) provider for adult continuous education
 - Vocational Training Center / VET institute
 - Association/Organization (local/ national/international)
 - Industry/Tourism Enterprise/hotel/resort/ tour operator
 - Club/ Lobby/NGO (non-governmental organization)/IGO (intergovernmental organization)
2. The educational programme/offer is for:
 - undergraduate students
 - postgraduate students

- adults with certified knowledge
- anyone (no requirements)
- employees of a company
- companies to train the employees
- other

3. The focus of the educational programme

Two lists were given, and a matching tool was offered to mark all the relevant matches

List A	List B
Hospitality	Management
Water sports tourism	Marketing
Tourism	Communication
Sports	Spatial Planning
Leisure	Sustainability
Sports tourism	Economy
Sustainable Tourism	Technical knowledge
Adventure Tourism	other
	Not specified

4. Country

5. Title of the Programme or the educational offer

6. Description/ overview of the programme or the educational offer

7. Type of educational/ training offer

- Educational/ Training program (consisting of many courses) (e.g. studies learning path, Master, PhD, etc.)
- Short course for Continuing Professional Development and Training
- In-campus Course (face-to-face teaching and learning)
- Online course/ MOOC (massive online open courses)/ digital
- Seminar/ workshop / summer or winter schools
- Internship/apprenticeship
- Convention
- Other

8. Elements that apply to this programme or educational/training offer:

- Certification
- accreditation
- university degree
- diploma
- license
- ECTS/ECVETS
- ISO

- Other
9. Duration:
- 1-15 days
 - 1-3 months
 - 1 semester
 - 1 year
 - 1-2 years
 - 3-4 years
 - Other

10. Fees

11. Frequency

- Annually
- Seasonal
- Quarterly
- On-Demand
- Other

12. Contact details (e-mail / website)

After extensive search and study of the educational and training offer in Water Sports and Tourism in Europe, data were checked for double entries, inaccurate or missing information, and all the existing curriculum models and syllabi were examined.

5 Findings

5.1 Water Sports Tourism Stakeholders

The initial mapping of the stakeholders, which lasted 3 months, reached 1760 data entries. This database is dynamic and will continuously be enriched for networking purposes and future collaboration. The main categories are:

Surf Clubs/ Schools

Accreditation Bodies

Media

Hotel chains/resorts

NGO's

Manufacturers

Risk Management/First Aid Organizations

Tour Operators

- The first category consists of **Schools, Clubs and Camps for watersports** and particular for surf, windsurf, kite and SUP. They are located at all water areas and all sea basins in Europe, on seacoasts, lakes, rivers and ocean coasts. All European countries offer water sports tourism products and services. They provide training and classes for tourists, but they also host academies of the accreditation bodies to train their personnel.
- The second category, the **accreditation bodies**, are organisations, associations and federations with affiliated clubs and sports academies. They organise events, competitions, provide coaching and training for their members. Unless they use their facilities, they are often hosted on surf clubs in various locations to provide instructor training. Trainees get a certificate or license after a short training, which can be upgraded to an upper level after another short course. After the training, instructors are asked to remain members of these associations as they function as a networking hub, for workforce circulation, upgrading instructors' level, informing for job vacancies, and various events.
- In the **Media** category we have gathered all print and online publications for water sports and coastal tourism. There are general publications that focus on all water sports, surface or underwater, or specialised publications for extreme watersports, adventure tourism, action sports, surfing, windsurfing, Kiteboarding, SUP. This study focuses on non-motorised water sports practiced on a board, and this the reason that all cruising, sailing, and diving publications (a very large category) was excluded for the present moment.

- A very interesting finding is that there is a large number of publications targeting to girls and women focusing on sports and gender issues and trying to promote the water sports lifestyle and empower and engage women to adopt it.
- This category also includes all communication channels, radio, TV and web TV channels, podcasts and webcasts, travel communities, and travel blogs dedicated to water sports, and of course social media and communication networks, groups and forums. The final list after detailed verification of data and updates will be available to all interested parties.
- The **Hotel/ Resorts** category includes all hotel chains or resorts located on sea/ocean coasts, rivers and lakes and provide water sports tourism services and products. Some of them have in their property aqua parks with pools and artificial waves for water sports. They usually offer jobs for 'water sports operators.
- The NGO's category includes all organisations, institutes, networks and unions that deal with marine and coastal issues, safety, conservation, legislation and environmental protection
- Manufacturers are also included in the water sports tourism stakeholders as they construct and provide equipment and they are also improving and testing new technologies and innovative materials on boards that may affect and change the way people kite and surf.
- The Risk management and first aid organisations are rescue teams, lifeguards, coast guard, port/coasts and navy authorities that are responsible for the safety, risk and crisis management, sea and ocean legislation.
- The last category of the stakeholders maps the tour operators that promote water sports and coastal tourism.

5.1.1 The educational and training offer in water sports tourism in Europe

The mapping of the educational and training offer in Europe lasted for 3 months. A first sample of 524 entries was collected, but after verification of data, many programmes were excluded from the present study, as significant information was missing or was not accurate and there were not valid contact details. Most of those programmes were mainly organised and offered occasionally for specific purposes by some surf clubs or associations.

The final sample consisted of 327 entries and was analysed according to the mapping tool.

According to the initial findings of the mapping procedure, there are multiple approaches with different focal points for "Water sports tourism" education and training provided by

a) universities,

b) colleges and academies for physical education and sports,

c) water sports associations and organisations.

Universities are offering multiple undergraduate and postgraduate Tourism and Hospitality studies focusing on general theoretical knowledge and more specific knowledge related to fields such as management, marketing and business administration. Within some curricula, courses are concentrated on adventure or sports tourism. Additional to the theoretical 3-year curricula, some universities are offering another year of work placement experience.

Several colleges and academies for physical education and sports are offering Recreation and Leisure studies, or Sports Tourism programmes.

The water sports organisations and associations are the only training providers that offer courses for multiple levels of professional training for water sports instructors and operators focusing on technical skills and some of them also on soft skills.

Country

- | | | | | | | | |
|-----------|-----------|------------|------------|-----------|--------------|-------------|---------------|
| ■ Cyprus | ■ Greece | ■ Poland | ■ UK | ■ Germany | ■ Finland | ■ Lithuania | ■ Netherlands |
| ■ Spain | ■ France | ■ Slovenia | ■ Latvia | ■ Austria | ■ Belgium | ■ Hungary | ■ Denmark |
| ■ Italy | ■ Romania | ■ Slovakia | ■ Bulgaria | ■ Estonia | ■ Luxemburg | ■ Malta | ■ Portugal |
| ■ Croatia | ■ Ireland | ■ Sweden | ■ Iceland | ■ India | ■ Kazakhstan | ■ Scotland | ■ Switzerland |

ELEMENTS THAT APPLY TO THIS EDUCATIONAL OFFER

Fees

6 Conclusion

Tourism sector is already under transformation and the new trends are expected to create new demands. The water sports tourism sector requires multi-skilled and educated professionals and is balancing between the circulation economy and the need to foster local employability for blue growth and sustainable development in coastal and rural areas. The three education models provided by a) **universities**, b) **colleges and academies for physical education and sports**, and c) **water sports associations and organisations** offer completely different knowledge base and skills and there is not specific specialisation for water sports professionals, apart from the short courses for technical training.

Hospitality tourism degrees alone are not enough for the needs of water sports tourism.

Certifications of water sports associations or sports academies are also not enough for blue professionals. Local employees sometimes have neither degrees nor certifications.

Water sports tourism emerges in all coastal areas in Europe and are vital for the local communities. Water sports tourists live their lives to the fullest, challenge themselves with new adventurous experiences and seek for tailor-made products (Morgan et al., 2005; Lam González et al., 2015). The age of the water sports tourists ranges from teenagers to seniors and the demand for more safety and precautions, extra facilities and more trained staff is apparent. Furthermore, as more holiday resorts are being transformed to accessible and friendly destinations for individuals with physical disabilities, adaptable infrastructure is required, and special training is needed.

Finally, water sports tourism professionals with ocean literacy and increased knowledge about the specific travel destination can add value to the touristic product in coastal areas. They can act as local ambassadors for the promotion of the travel destination and can raise awareness about the preservation of our seas and the aquaculture.

The current education and training systems do not satisfy the needs of the new, emerging tourism industry that is more global, more demanding and more diverse than ever. Acknowledging the importance of quality education in the hospitality and tourism sector, strategic alliances and cooperation between industry, academia and vocational institutions can redesign curricula to meet the demands of the industry. Educated and highly skilled tourism professionals can contribute to the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals and the urgent need for the preservation of our blue and green environment for resilience and a prosperous future.

7 Limitation of the study

The water sports referred to and examined in this study are those practiced on a board such as 'windsurfing', 'kitesurfing', 'surfing', 'SUP' that are the focus of the NAUTILUS PROJECT.

The educational programmes presented in the study were examined through the existing information of their websites. A quantitative and qualitative approach was used for the data analysis. Verification of the data or their updates through face to face interaction or communication was not possible due to the European quarantine or missing contact data. Several educational entries were excluded from the study because of the missing data or insufficient description and are saved for future research.

Another limitation was the mapping of the Surf schools' training programmes. Although there is a great amount of surf schools, there was not possible to retrieve information about their training activities because most of them maintain only Social Media accounts with audio-visual content and limited information, or they are just listed in catalogues or press announcements. For this reason, this category will be examined in the next step of our study during the training and skills needs analysis where face to face or virtual interaction is planned.

This study presents the categories of the water sports tourism stakeholders and educational providers to indicate the ground and offer the opportunity for networking activities, contacts and future collaboration. A dynamic database is constantly updated to create the networking hub for the education and certification framework that we are going to develop.

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9 Appendix 1

The Mapping tool used for data collection

Mapping of the water sports tourism education and training

Online web-search for the educational and training offer in water sports tourism (formal/informal/non formal) using INDICATIVELY search terms like the following in all possible combinations:

"tourism" AND "education", "training", "vocational training" AND "water sports", "water sports tourism education", "water sports tourism training", "water sports trainer", "water sports academy", "water sports AND tourism", "Curriculum", "Course" AND water sports tourism", "higher education AND water sports tourism", "water sports tourism AND adult education/training", "windsurfing" AND "courses", etc.

Use all the terms referred to in the papers that were given to you and the pilot study

* Απαιτείται

Training/ Educational Provider

- Higher Education/University/Faculty/School/Department (formal education)
- Public/Private Academy or College (formal education)
- Public/Private Vocational Education and Training (VET) school
- VET (Vocational Education and Training) provider for adult continuous education
- Vocational Training Center / VET institute
- Association/Organization (local/ national/international)
- Industry/Tourism Enterprise/hotel/resort/ tour operator
- Club/ Lobby/NGO
- other (please specify it in the next section)

Name of the affiliation/organization *

Η απάντησή σας _____

Website (link) *

Η απάντησή σας _____

The educational programme/offer is for

Επιλογή ▼

If 'other' please specify:

Η απάντησή σας _____

The educational offer focuses on

	Management	Marketing	Communication	Spatial Planning	Sustainability	Economic Studies
Hospitality	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Water sports tourism	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Tourism	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Water sports	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Sports	<input type="checkbox"/>					

<p>If 'other' please specify:</p> <p>Η απάντησή σας _____</p>
<p>Country</p> <p>Η απάντησή σας _____</p>
<p>Title of the Programme or the educational offer</p> <p>Η απάντησή σας _____</p>

<p>Description/ overview of the Programme or the educational offer</p> <p>Η απάντησή σας _____</p>
--

<p>Type of educational/ training offer</p> <p>Επιλογή ▼</p>

<p>If 'other' please specify:</p> <p>Η απάντησή σας _____</p>

Check below elements that apply to this educational offer (check more than one if applicable)

- certification
- accreditation
- university degree
- diploma
- ECTS/ ECVETS
- verified
- ISO
- Άλλο: _____

Duration

Επιλογή ▼

If 'other' please specify:

Η απάντησή σας _____

Fees?

- Yes
- No
- unknown information

If there are fees, how much?

Η απάντησή σας _____

Frequency

Επιλογή ▼

If 'other' please specify:

Η απάντησή σας _____

E-mail address

Η απάντησή σας _____

Υποβολή